

number of acetoxymercuri derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones (IV) were prepared by condensing mercuric acetate with 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones.

Acetoxymercuri derivative of 5-benzylidene-3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-*p*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone was also prepared by condensing mercuric acetate with 5-benzylidene 3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-*p*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone in aqueous acetic acid medium.

The ultra violet spectra of several 5-benzylidene-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinone prepared during the present work were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 recording spectrometer and are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF SOME 5-BENZYLIDENE-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONE

Compounds	EtOH max (m μ)
1. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-2- <i>p</i> -fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	236,335
2. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>p</i> -iodophenyl-2- <i>p</i> -iodophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	237,268
3. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>p</i> -nitrophenyl-2- <i>p</i> -nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	235,375

Fungicidal test : The fungicidal activity of some 5-benzylidene-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and 3-acetoxymercuriaryl-2-acetoxymercuriarylimino-4-thiazolidinones were determined by the method of Horsfall¹⁷ and the percentage inhibitions are summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

Experimental

5-Benzylidene-3-*o*-fluorophenyl-2-*o*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : 3-*o*-Fluorophenyl-2-*o*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (2 g.) and benzaldehyde (8 ml.) were refluxed in presence of pyridine (10 ml.) in an oil bath at 150°-60° for 5 hr. After completion of reaction, the clear liquid was poured in cold water

with continuous stirring. The solution was kept overnight when a yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed well with hot water and dil. HCl and recrystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 155°; yield, 1.6 g. (62%).

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 5-BENZYLIDENE-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES(I)*

Compound	% inhibition at conc.		
	1 : 1000	1 : 10000	1 : 100000
1. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-2- <i>p</i> -fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	79.7	23.4	9.7
2. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>p</i> -iodophenyl-2- <i>p</i> -iodophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	84.0	57.7	36.0
3. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	94.9	88.0	50.9
5. 5-Benzylidene-3- <i>m</i> -nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	85.9	64.0	36.0

* By the method of Horsfall¹⁷.

TABLE 3—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 3-ACETOXYMERCURIARYL-2-ACETOXYMERCURIARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES(IV)*

Compound	% inhibition at conc.		
	1 : 1000	1 : 10000	1 : 100000
1. 3-Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	96.0	94.9	66.9
2. 3-Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -iodophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -iodophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	92.4	81.9	64.0
3. 3-Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	97.9	96.0	84.0
4. 3-Acetoxymercuri- <i>m</i> -nitrophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri- <i>m</i> -nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone	92.4	74.9	47.4
5. 3-Acetoxymercuri-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-acetoxymercuri-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)imino-4-thiazolidinone	97.7	93.7	60.9

* By the method of Horsfall¹⁷.

Physical constants and analytical data of the 5-arylidene derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones prepared as above are given in Table 4.

5-Phenylazo-3-o-fluorophenyl-2-o-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone: Aniline (2 ml.) was dissolved in 5 ml. of conc. hydrochloric acid and 5 ml. of water. The solution was cooled to 0° in an ice-bath and diazotised with ice-cold solution of sodium nitrate (1.5 g. in 10 ml. water). A solution of 3-o-fluorophenyl-2-o-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (0.7 g. dissolved in 10 ml. of acetone and 10 ml. of acetic acid) was added slowly to this diazotised solution. After about half an hour the mixture was diluted with water and kept overnight when a dark brown precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed well with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 162°; yield, 0.61 g. (65%).

By the above method sixteen 5-arylazoderivatives of 4-thiazolidinones have been prepared and their properties are described in Table 5.

5-m-Tolyl-3-p-fluorophenyl-2-p-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone: *m*-Toluidine (4 ml.) dissolved in 10 ml. of concd. hydrochloric acid and 10 ml. of water was diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrate (2.4 g. in 20 ml. water). This cold diazo solution was then added slowly to a precooled solution of 3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-*p*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (4 g. dissolved in 30 ml. of acetone and 20 ml. of

ethanol) containing 4 g. of suspended crystals of sodium acetate.

A solution of cupric chloride (4 g. in 30 ml of water) was then added slowly with stirring in about 2 hr. and the reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath at 50° till the evolution of nitrogen ceased. The solution was acidified with dil. HCl and kept for half an hour. The precipitate was collected, washed several times with water and finally with acetone to remove any 4-thiazolidinone. The product was recrystallised from ethanol to give 5-*m*-tolyl-3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-*p*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone m.p., 151° (dec.); yield, 2.8 g. (54%).

By applying the above method a number of 5-aryl-3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been prepared. Their physical and analytical data are given in Table 6.

3-Acetoxymercuri-o-fluorophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri-o-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone: 3-*o*-Fluorophenyl-2-*o*-fluorophenylamino-4-thiazolidinone (3 g.), dissolved in ethanol (20 ml.) and glacial acetic acid (30 ml.) and a solution of mercuric acetate (6 g. in 30 ml. water and 15 ml. glacial acetic acid) were refluxed directly on an asbestos wire gauze for 10 min. After the completion of the reaction a precipitate appeared. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with 70 ml. of water. The precipitate was collected, washed several times with hot water, dil.

TABLE 4—5-ARYLIDENE-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES(I)

S.N.	Ar group	Ar' group	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %				
						C	H	N	S	
1.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	Phenyl	155	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ OS	Found	67.38	3.49	7.29	8.24
						Calc.	67.34	3.57	7.14	8.16
2.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	Phenyl	207-9	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ OS	Found	67.41	3.62	7.02	8.22
						Calc.	67.34	3.57	7.14	8.16
3.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	Phenyl	180	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₂ OS	Found	43.46	2.39	4.38	5.39
						Calc.	43.42	2.30	4.60	5.26
4.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	154	61	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found	68.23	4.32	7.61	8.32
						Calc.	68.04	4.12	7.21	8.24
5.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	300	69	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found	68.22	4.32	7.34	8.36
						Calc.	68.04	4.12	7.21	8.24
6.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	271-72	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found	68.11	4.21	7.18	8.35
						Calc.	68.04	4.12	7.21	8.24
7.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	68	64	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found	59.22	3.41	12.61	7.28
						Calc.	59.19	3.14	12.56	7.17
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	108	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found	59.26	3.22	12.25	7.20
						Calc.	59.19	3.14	12.56	7.17
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	141	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found	59.28	3.25	21.21	7.24
						Calc.	59.19	3.14	12.56	7.17
10.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	234	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	Found	64.77	3.51	6.72	7.88
						Calc.	64.70	3.43	6.86	7.84

TABLE 5—5-ARYLAZO-3-ARYL-2-ARYLAMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (II)

S.No.	Ar. group	Ar' group	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formular	Analysis %				
						C	H	N	S	
1.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	Phenyl	162	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	61.43	3.58	13.82	7.97
						Calc.	61.76	3.43	13.72	7.84
2.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	Phenyl	120	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	61.89	3.52	13.68	7.88
						Calc.	61.76	3.43	13.72	7.84
3.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	102	71	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ F ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	62.72	3.85	13.41	7.76
						Calc.	62.55	3.79	13.27	7.58
4.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	180	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ F ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	62.35	3.41	13.38	7.74
						Calc.	62.55	3.79	13.27	7.58
5.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>α</i> -Naphthyl	104	70	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ F ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	65.72	3.58	12.44	7.41
						Calc.	65.50	3.49	12.22	6.99
6.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	124	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ F ₂ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	51.38	3.36	14.58	13.42
						Calc.	51.74	3.08	14.37	13.14
7.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	132	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	63.35	4.44	13.42	7.82
						Calc.	63.15	4.30	13.39	7.65
8.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>α</i> -Naphthyl	105	65	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₈ S	Found	66.37	3.62	12.55	7.35
						Calc.	66.08	3.96	12.33	7.04
9.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	130	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	52.44	3.76	14.74	13.66
						Calc.	52.17	3.52	14.49	13.25
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	108	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	Found	54.42	3.18	18.31	6.68
						Calc.	54.54	3.03	18.18	6.92
11.	<i>o</i> -Iodophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	154	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ I ₂ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	35.69	2.22	9.79	9.31
						Calc.	35.84	2.13	9.98	9.10
12.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	130	66	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ I ₂ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	35.79	2.36	9.68	9.26
						Calc.	35.84	2.13	9.98	9.10
13.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	165	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	52.28	3.62	11.51	13.22
						Calc.	52.17	3.52	14.49	13.66
14.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	115d	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₇ S ₂	Found	46.62	2.71	18.35	11.78
						Calc.	46.58	2.77	18.11	11.83
15.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	118	66	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	42.44	2.61	11.46	10.66
						Calc.	42.78	2.20	11.88	10.86
16.	<i>p</i> -Tribromophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphon- amidophenyl	92	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Br ₃ N ₅ O ₈ S ₂	Found	27.36	1.27	7.92	6.78
						Calc.	27.24	1.18	7.56	6.92

acetic acid and finally with ethanol. The compound was obtained as white shining crystals which turned yellow on heating at 200°, orange at 225° and melted at 238°; yield, 5.2 g. (74%).

By the same method several 3-acetoxymercuiriaryl-2-acetoxymercuiriaryl-amino-4-thiazolidinones were prepared which are listed in Table 7 alongwith their physical and analytical data.

3-Acetoxymercuri-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-acetoxymercuri-*p*-fluorophenylimino-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone : 5-Benzylidene-3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2-*p*-fluorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (1.5 g.) on mercuriation by the above method gave 2.4 g. (66%) of the acetoxymercuri derivative, m.p. 219°.

Analysis : Found : C, 34.58; H, 1.66; N, 3.36; S, 3.25; Hg, 44.44; C₂₆H₁₈F₂N₂O₅SHg₂ requires C, 34.36; H, 1.98; N, 3.08; S, 3.52; Hg, 44.05%

TABLE 6—5-ARYL-3-ARYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (III)

S.No.	Ag. group	Ar' group	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis%			
						C	H	N	S
1.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	151d.	54	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ F ₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	Found 66.88 Calc. 67.00	4.15 4.06	7.46 7.11	8.42 8.12
2.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	159	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ I ₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	Found 43.44 Calc. 43.28	2.91 2.62	4.78 4.59	5.64 5.24
3.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	165	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found 67.98 Calc. 67.69	4.82 4.61	7.34 7.18	8.42 8.20
4.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	155	62	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found 67.92 Calc. 67.69	4.21 4.61	7.48 7.18	8.59 8.20
5.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	180	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	Found 67.44 Calc. 67.69	4.91 4.61	7.50 7.18	8.61 8.20
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	170	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅ S	Found 59.39 Calc. 58.93	3.32 3.57	12.81 12.50	7.46 7.14
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	187	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅ S	Found 59.41 Calc. 58.93	3.88 3.57	12.26 12.50	7.38 7.14
8.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	126-27	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ S	Found 53.46 Calc. 53.22	2.56 2.82	5.92 5.64	6.72 6.45
9.	<i>s</i> -Tribromophenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	89	78	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ Br ₃ N ₂ O ₅ S	Found 31.52 Calc. 31.73	1.81 1.44	3.62 3.36	3.52 3.84
10.	<i>o</i> -Iodophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	180	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ I ₂ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	Found 37.52 Calc. 37.33	2.43 2.22	6.51 6.22	9.90 9.48
11.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	245	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	Found 55.52 Calc. 55.38	3.46 3.73	9.44 9.23	14.32 14.06
12.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	158	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S ₂	Found 55.61 Calc. 55.38	3.36 3.73	9.51 9.23	14.40 14.06
13.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	101	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₇ S ₂	Found 49.52 Calc. 49.12	2.48 2.92	13.92 13.64	12.61 12.25
14.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	120	61	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₇ S ₂	Found 49.55 Calc. 49.12	2.48 2.92	13.47 13.64	12.68 12.48
15.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	190	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	Found 44.58 Calc. 44.92	2.62 2.32	7.88 7.48	11.76 11.41
16.	<i>s</i> -Tribromophenyl	<i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl	164	66	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Br ₃ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	Found 28.38 Calc. 28.09	1.52 1.22	4.98 4.68	7.44 7.13

TABLE 7—3-ACETOXYMERCURIARYL-2-ACETOXYMERCURIARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDINONES (IV)

S.No.	Ag. group	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis%				
					C	H	N	S	Hg
1.	<i>o</i> -Fluorophenyl	238	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 27.62 Calc. 27.80	1.92 1.70	3.68 3.41	3.61 3.90	48.42 48.78
2.	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	245	76	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 27.66 Calc. 27.80	1.52 1.70	3.75 3.41	3.59 3.90	49.02 48.78
3.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenyl	242	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 24.40 Calc. 24.20	1.68 1.48	2.48 2.96	3.55 3.39	42.79 42.96
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	248-49	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 24.44 Calc. 24.20	1.76 1.49	3.24 2.97	3.66 3.39	42.62 42.96
5.	<i>o</i> -Iodophenyl	251	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 22.35 Calc. 22.00	1.52 1.35	2.34 2.70	3.36 3.08	38.92 38.61
6.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	218	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 22.32 Calc. 22.00	1.62 1.35	2.42 2.70	3.38 3.08	39.04 38.61
7.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	200 Shrinks	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ SHg ₂	Found 27.58 Calc. 27.94	1.62 1.96	3.74 3.43	3.56 3.92	49.40 49.02
8.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	212	52	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ SHg ₂	Found 27.62 Calc. 27.94	1.71 1.96	3.68 3.43	3.66 3.92	49.40 49.02
9.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	300	62	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ SHg ₂	Found 27.59 Calc. 27.94	1.54 1.96	3.71 3.43	3.68 3.92	49.36 49.02
10.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	250	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₉ SHg ₂	Found 26.44 Calc. 26.08	1.87 1.60	6.88 6.40	3.26 3.66	45.95 45.76
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	268	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₉ SHg ₂	Found 26.38 Calc. 26.08	1.24 1.60	6.65 6.40	3.24 3.66	45.44 45.76
12.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	250d.	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ SHg ₂	Found 24.48 Calc. 24.72	1.52 1.30	3.37 3.03	3.71 3.47	43.67 43.38

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